

Rotating Wave Dynamics in Rings of Coupled Oscillators: A Comprehensive Review

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This comprehensive review paper provides a thorough survey of the extensive research conducted on rotating waves observed in rings of coupled oscillators. These waves manifest as stable periodic, quasiperiodic, or chaotic orbits, arising from the phase difference between neighboring oscillators. The research encompasses a wide range of nonlinear systems, including electrical circuits, neural models, Duffing, Lorenz, and Rössler oscillators, among others. While exploring the behavior of rotating waves, particular emphasis is placed on neural oscillators, as neural rings in the brain play a crucial role in working memory. The intricate dynamics of rotating waves are elucidated through the application of various techniques, including time series analysis, phase-space analysis, bifurcation diagrams, spectral analysis, and basins of attraction. These methods carefully uncover the complex routes from coexisting stable equilibria to hyperchaos. The study highlights a sequence of bifurcations occurring with increasing coupling strength, such as the Andronov–Hopf, torus, and crisis bifurcations. Moreover, the coexistence of multiple rotating waves under the same system parameters is examined. The vast body of research on rotating waves provides insights that are essential for a wide range of scientific disciplines and real-world applications, including lasers, chemical reactions, cardiorespiratory systems, and even beyond, with particular relevance to neural networks and brain functions.

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1. Introduction

The investigation of collective dynamics in coupled oscillators has garnered significant attention from researchers spanning diverse scientific disciplines. Its wide-ranging applications in engineering, biomedicine, and communications have contributed to its appeal [1]. Particularly, the study of synchronous dynamics in networks of coupled oscillators has captivated interest, considering the pervasive presence of complex networks in our daily lives, such as various transport, energy, communication, social, and neural networks [2]. Among different network structures, the ring configuration holds special significance due to its capacity to generate

rotating waves propagating along the ring of interconnected nodes [3–7].

The interest to a study of the rings of coupled oscillators increased in connection with physiological and biochemical systems. A notable contribution to this field is the pioneering work of Turing [8], who developed a based model of morphogenesis that proved useful in studying slow wave activity in the mammalian gut [9]. However, the most intriguing application was found in the field of neuronal systems, in particular, in the study of central pattern generators (CPGs), which have been shown to play important roles in peripheral neural systems, locomotion, etc. [10]. CPGs are networks of neurons in the central nervous system capable of generating autonomous rhythmic outputs, such as breathing, walking, or running, without relying on sensory feedback from

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the associated moving organs. Although current neurophysiological techniques face challenges in isolating such circuits amidst the intricate neural connections of complex animals, there exist strong indirect experimental evidences supporting their existence [11–13].

In addition, rings of coupled electronic oscillators which resemble CPGs, have emerged as an interesting approach in the design and control of legged robots. These oscillators produce a stable and natural variety of phase relationships [14]. Notably, Collins and Stewart [15, 16] conducted a fascinating study on animals with a small number of legs, aiming to elucidate the patterns of oscillations, i.e., the gaits, used by these animals during locomotion [17]. Their analysis involved examining the periodic states that arise through a symmetric Andronov–Hopf bifurcation from the basic standing gait, employing simple symmetric networks of coupled identical cells.

The emergence of a rotating wave can be attributed to the phase difference between adjacent oscillators, causing it to propagate along a ring-shaped structure. Initially observed in the late 1970s within the context of reaction-diffusion systems in an annular reactor [18–20], experimental confirmation of rotating phase waves was achieved a decade later [21]. These waves manifest when a previously homogeneous state becomes linearly unstable in the Andronov–Hopf bifurcation [22]. Although progress in this field was limited during the following decade, research regained momentum in the mid-1990s, likely fueled by advancements in nonlinear science and computer technology. Notably, Nekorkin et al. [23] identified rotational waves in a ring of coupled bistable phase generators with sinusoidal nonlinearity, while Matias et al. [24, 25] discovered similar rotating waves in rings of unidirectionally coupled Chua and Lorenz oscillators. These significant findings have spurred numerous researchers to delve into the study of rotating waves.

It is worth noting that previous investigations into synchronous dynamics

in ring networks of coupled oscillators have primarily focused on bidirectional coupling [26–30], including bistable oscillators [27–29]. In such systems, weak coupling gives rise to a standing pulse wave. However, once the coupling strength surpasses a critical threshold, the standing pulse wave transforms into a propagating pulse wave, which in certain cases becomes chaotic and unpredictably changes its propagation direction.

The study of unidirectionally coupled systems is highly significant as it enables signal transmission between subsystems without receiving feedback. Investigating unidirectional rings has revealed intriguing dynamics. In particular, the increasing coupling strength gives rise to a series of torus bifurcations where transitions from stable equilibrium states to quasiperiodicity, and then to chaos and hyperchaos were observed in rings of coupled Chua [25, 31], Lorenz [32–38], Rössler [39], Duffing [40–43], Chen [44, 45], Bonhoeffer–van der Pol [46], Stuart–Landau [47, 48], FitzHugh–Nagumo [47], and Rulkov [49–51] oscillators, as well as in electronic circuits [52], semiconductor [53] and fiber lasers [54]. In addition, unidirectional communication plays an important role in neural networks [55–57].

The analysis and characterization of rotating waves carry particular relevance in the fields of neuroscience and medicine, providing insights into phenomena such as cardiorespiratory interactions [58], traveling electrical waves in the cortex [59], and similar phenomena [60, 61].

In this paper, we review the results on the study of rotating waves in unidirectional rings of coupled oscillators shown in Fig. 1 composed by different dynamical systems, including Duffing, Lorenz, and Rössler oscillators, as well as lasers and neurons.

2. Ring of Duffing Oscillators

The Duffing oscillator is renowned among dynamical systems for its versatility as a generic model and its wide applicability across

FIG. 1. The ring of N unidirectionally coupled oscillators with rotating waves propagating along the ring.

various physical systems. It serves as a valuable representation for different scenarios, such as slender aerostructures susceptible to buckling under loads [62], microelectromechanical switches [63], vibration-based energy harvesters [64, 65], electrical circuits [66], and optical systems [67]. This oscillator exhibits a broad range of dynamics, including multistability and oscillation death [68]. The stability properties of a ring of coupled Duffing oscillators have been extensively investigated, both in the case of the simplest network with three nodes [42, 69–71] and in larger networks involving a higher number of oscillators [41, 72].

Several studies have focused on investigating the bifurcations that occur during the transition from a stable steady state to hyperchaos in coupled Duffing oscillators, with a particular emphasis on the influence of the coupling strength [41, 73–76]. These investigations have revealed that along this path, the oscillators experience the Andronov-Hopf bifurcation followed by a series of torus bifurcations.

2.1. Model of coupled Duffing oscillators

The behavior of a cyclic ring consisting of N identical double-well damped Duffing

oscillators can be mathematically represented by the following system of second-order differential equations:

$$\begin{aligned} \ddot{x}_1 + a\dot{x}_1 + \omega_0^2 x_1 + \delta x_1^3 + \sigma(x_1 - x_N) &= 0, \\ \ddot{x}_2 + a\dot{x}_2 + \omega_0^2 x_2 + \delta x_2^3 + \sigma(x_2 - x_1) &= 0, \\ &\vdots \\ \ddot{x}_N + a\dot{x}_N + \omega_0^2 x_N + \delta x_N^3 + \sigma(x_N - x_{N-1}) &= 0, \end{aligned} \quad (2.1)$$

where $a = 0.4$, $\omega_0^2 = -0.25$, $\delta = 0.5$ are constants [42, 70, 77] and σ is the coupling strength used as a control parameter.

When uncoupled, each oscillator stays in one of two stable fixed points ($x_{1,2}^* = \pm\sqrt{|\omega_0^2|/\delta} = \pm\sqrt{1/2}$, $\dot{x}_{1,2}^* \equiv y_{1,2}^* = 0$). However, being unidirectionally coupled in the ring, the system exhibits very rich dynamics from coexisting stable fixed points to hyperchaos as the coupling strength σ is increased.

2.2. Routes to chaos and hyperchaos

Since all oscillators are identical, in Fig. 1 we plot the bifurcations diagrams of the local maxima x^{max} of one of the oscillators in cyclic rings composed of $N = 3, 4, 5, 6$ oscillators. We do not show here the bifurcation diagrams for the rings with more than six oscillators since they look very similar.

The bifurcation scenarios on the route from stable steady states to chaos and hyperchaos strongly depend on the number of oscillators in rings with a small number of oscillators ($N < 6$). Specifically, the following routes are observed.

a. Ring of $N = 3$ oscillators. In the smallest ring of three oscillators, for very small coupling ($\sigma < 0.35$), two original fixed points $FP_{1,2}$ at $(x_{1,2}^* = \pm\sqrt{1/2}, y_{1,2}^* = 0)$ coexist. At $\sigma \approx 0.35$ a stable limit cycle appears and coexists with these two fixed points. At $\sigma \approx 0.5$ the limit cycle undergoes the first torus bifurcation, after which the oscillators' behavior becomes quasiperiodic, and at $\sigma \approx 1.2$ the system undergoes the second torus bifurcation where its dynamics becomes chaotic. Finally, for $\sigma > 3.1$

FIG. 2. Bifurcation diagrams of (upper panels) local maxima of x and (lower panels) two largest Lyapunov exponents $\lambda_{1,2}$ versus coupling strength σ for randomly chosen initial conditions in the range $-10 < x(0), y(0) < 10$ ($y(0) \equiv \dot{x}(0)$) for rings of (a) $N = 3$, (b) $N = 4$, (c) $N = 5$, and (d) $N = 6$ Duffing oscillators. (Color online)

the system becomes hyperchaotic due to external crisis. These results are in a good agreement with our previous observations [42].

b. Ring of $N = 4$ oscillators. A distinct route is observed in the ring of four oscillators. In this ring, as well as in larger rings with even number of oscillators, a hidden attractor with zero amplitude known as *amplitude death* (AD) arises at $\sigma = 0.125$ in the inverse supercritical pitchfork bifurcation, in which two stable fixed points $FP_{3,4}$ merge into a single zero fixed point ($x = \dot{x} \equiv y = 0$) (AD), which coexists with two original stable equilibria $FP_{1,2}$ for $\sigma > 0.125$. As the coupling strength is further increased, a stable limit cycle arises at $\sigma \approx 0.2$ and gradually transforms into a quasiperiodic orbit. Then, a chaotic orbit suddenly appears at $\sigma = 1.2$ and disappears at $\sigma = 3.4$. The chaotic and quasiperiodic orbits coexist for $1.2 < \sigma < 3.4$. The time series of the coexisting chaotic and two quasiperiodic orbits for

$\sigma = 1.5$ are presented in Fig. 2. For $3.5 < \sigma < 3.8$, there is a periodic window which coexists with AD.

c. Ring of $N = 5$ oscillators. In the ring of five oscillators, a stable limit cycle arises at $\sigma = 0.224$ and transforms into a quasiperiodic orbit at $\sigma = 1.04$ in the torus bifurcation. Then, at $\sigma = 1.136$ a crisis bifurcation gives rise to chaos, which finally transforms into a torus at $\sigma \approx 3.75$.

d. Ring of $N \geq 6$ oscillators. The route to hyperchaos is similar in the rings with larger than five oscillators ($N > 5$). The difference only exists between the rings with even and odd number of oscillators for $\sigma > 0.05$. Specifically, in all rings with even number of oscillators two stable fixed points merge into a stable zero equilibrium (AD) in the inverse pitchfork bifurcation.

It is very important to note that as the number of nodes N is increased, hyperchaos arises at smaller values of the coupling strength both in

the case of even and odd number of oscillators.

2.3. Coexistence of rotating waves

Furthermore, different coexisting attractors appear and disappear depending on the coupling strength and the number of oscillators in the ring. The occurrence of multiple attractors in coupled oscillators is an intriguing phenomenon that deserves significant scrutiny [78]. The interplay between the coupling strength and the number of oscillators in the ring plays a pivotal role in shaping the system dynamics. For instance, in the ring of $N = 11$ oscillators, 32 stable fixed point coexists for very weak coupling ($\sigma < 0.06$). For stronger coupling ($0.06 < \sigma < 0.275$), 11 attractors coexists including two original fixed points and 9 periodic orbits born in the Andronov-Hopf bifurcation at $\sigma \approx 0.6$. As σ is further increased ($0.275 < \sigma < 0.34$), the system's dynamics becomes chaotic, while the two original fixed points still coexist. Finally, for very strong coupling ($\sigma > 0.34$), only the chaotic attractor remains.

The structure of the basins of some coexisting attractors can be seen in Fig. 3 which shows the projection of the basins of attraction on the $(x_1(0), y_1(0))$ plane for the ring of $N = 11$ oscillators. The basins of multiple coexisting attractors are visualized using distinct colors. Despite this reduction in dimensionality, we can still observe a significant number of coexisting attractors within the system.

The multiple oscillatory attractors give rise to rotating waves that circulate along a ring.

2.4. Wave speed and frequency

Firstly, it is necessary to determine the instantaneous phase of the rotating wave. This can be achieved by employing the Hilbert transform, which is widely utilized for analyzing oscillatory and wave-like signals. The Hilbert transform operates on a real-valued function $x(t)$ and generates a complex-valued function $\hat{x}(t)$ that

FIG. 3. Projection of basins of attraction of coexisting states on the $(x_1(0), y_1(0))$ plane for the ring $N = 11$ Duffing oscillators at $\sigma = 0.18$. The largest basins belong to symmetric heteroclinic orbit (HeS), double-loop homoclinic orbit (HoDL₁), fixed points (FP_{1,2,4}), asymmetric heteroclinic orbit (HeA₁), and double-loop heteroclinic orbit (HeDL₁). The following initial conditions are used: $x_{3,5,7,9,11}(0) = 0.7071$, $x_{2,4,6,8,10}(0) = -0.7071$, $y_{2-11}(0) = 0$. (Color online)

provides insights into the instantaneous phase and amplitude of the original signal. Mathematically, the Hilbert transform is defined as the convolution of the original signal with the function $1/(\pi t)$ (or its principal value), expressed as follows:

$$\hat{x}(t) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{x(\tau)}{t - \tau} d\tau. \quad (2.2)$$

From a geometric perspective, the Hilbert transform can be understood as a 90-degree phase shift for each frequency component of the signal. This transformation leads to the creation of the analytic signal, represented as $z(t) = x(t) + i\hat{x}(t)$. By incorporating both positive and negative frequency components, this complex-valued representation fully captures the essence of the original signal. The phase $\Phi(t)$ is subsequently determined from the argument of $z(t)$, derived as

$$\Phi(t) = \arctan \left(\frac{\hat{x}(t) - \hat{x}(t_0)}{x(t) - x(t_0)} \right). \quad (2.3)$$

The rotating waves are visualized with the times series in Fig. 4. This figure provides a

FIG. 4. (a–d) Rotating wave time series and (e–h) phase portraits of corresponding attractors in the ring of $N = 11$ oscillators for (a,e) $\sigma = 0.18$ (homoclinic orbit Ho_2), (b,f) $\sigma = 0.192$ (asymmetric heteroclinic orbit HeA_2), (c,g) $\sigma = 0.236$ (symmetric heteroclinic orbit HeS), and (d,h) $\sigma = 0.308$ (chaos). T_p is the phase propagation time from node 1 to node 11, α is the inclination angle which defines wave speed \mathcal{W} derived by Eq. 2.4. (Color online)

comprehensive view of the wave dynamics in the ring of $N = 11$ Duffing oscillators for four different values of the coupling strength: $\sigma = 0.18$, $\sigma = 0.192$, $\sigma = 0.236$, and $\sigma = 0.308$. One can see that the time series of each oscillator varies only in terms of its phase, leading to phase shifts between consecutive nodes. These collective phase shifts form the wave that propagates around the cyclic ring.

Figures 4(a–d) show the time series patterns of all oscillators showcasing their dynamical behavior over time, while the lower row displays the phase portraits of the corresponding attractors representing their structure in the (x_i, y_i) projection, where $i = 1, \dots, N$. The rotating waves are visually represented by oblique stripes observed in the time series. The inclination angle α of these oblique stripes, as marked in Fig. 4(a) for illustration purposes, determines the phase shift velocity, commonly referred to as the wave speed \mathcal{W} . At the same time, the wave frequency f_w can be determined from the time series as the inverse period (wavelength) T_w of oscillations, i.e. $f_w = 1/T_w$. Alternatively, it can

be revealed by examining the power spectra of the time series as the frequency of the dominant spectral component.

It should be noted that the phase portraits in Figs. 4(e–h) remain consistent across all oscillators since they are identical. An interesting observation is that the attractor’s size enlarges as the coupling strength is increased.

Mathematically, the rotating wave speed can be calculated as follows:

$$\mathcal{W} = \arctan \frac{T_p}{N - 1}, \quad (2.4)$$

where T_p is the phase propagation time from node 1 to node N . One can see that $\mathcal{W} = \alpha$ decreases as the coupling strength is increased.

Figure 5(a) illustrates how the speeds of the coexisting rotating waves depend on the coupling strength σ . One can see that all waves propagate at approximately the same speed, exhibiting an almost exponential decay as σ is increased.

Finally, Fig. 5(b) displays the relationship between the wave frequency f_w and σ . It can be observed that each wave possesses its own frequency, which exhibits an almost linear growth

FIG. 5. (a) Speed W and (b) frequency f_w of the coexisting rotating waves as a function of the coupling strength σ in the ring of $N = 11$ oscillators. HeS is the heteroclinic symmetric orbit, HeA_{1,2} are heteroclinic asymmetric orbits, Ho_{1,2} are homoclinic orbits, HoDL_{1,2} are double-loop homoclinic orbits, and HeDL_{1,2} are double-loop heteroclinic orbits. (Color online)

as the coupling strength σ is elevated. It is worth noting that the orbits that arise at higher coupling strengths tend to have higher frequencies.

Thus, the rotating waves in the ring of unidirectionally coupled double-well Duffing oscillators exhibit intricate dynamics. The wave speed can be determined by analyzing the time series patterns, specifically by examining the inclination angle of parallel stripes. At the same time, the wave velocity remains approximately constant for all coexisting limit cycles, but experiences almost exponential growth

with increasing coupling strength. Conversely, the wave frequency differs among the various coexisting attractors and demonstrates an almost linear increase with coupling strength. These findings hold significance for comprehending the dynamics of information transfer in complex networks featuring cyclic ring motifs [49, 79].

3. Ring of Lorenz Oscillators

Let us now consider rotating waves in the ring of Lorenz oscillators.

Rotating wave dynamics in the ring of three unidirectionally coupled Lorenz oscillators was investigated by various researchers [32–38]. This model was also implemented into an experimental circuit [35]. Similar to Duffing oscillators, the wave dynamics of the ring of Lorenz oscillators exhibits the transition from periodic orbits to quasiperiodic and chaotic waves. The experimental study confirmed the robustness of this route.

3.1. Model of coupled Lorenz oscillators

The dynamics of the ring of three unidirectionally coupled Lorenz oscillators is described by the following system of equations:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{x}_i &= \sigma(y_i - x_i), \\ \dot{y}_i &= Rx_j - y_i - x_i z_i, \\ \dot{z}_i &= x_i y_i - bz_i, \end{aligned} \quad (3.1)$$

where $x_j = x_{i-1}$ if $i \neq 1$ and $x_j = x_3$ otherwise.

Depending on the system parameters, Sánchez et al. [35] observed either fixed points or oscillatory regimes in the ring of coupled Lorenz oscillators. These regimes are localized in different regions of the parameter space, as illustrated in Fig. 6.

For small values of R , in the interval $R \in [29, 38]$, the stable solution of Eq. (3.1) is only fixed point (FP) $C_{\pm} = (\pm\sqrt{b(R-1)}, \pm\sqrt{b(R-1)}, R-1)$, so that all Lyapunov exponents are negative.

FIG. 6. Regions of dynamical regimes in the (R, σ) space in the ring of Lorenz oscillators given by Eqs. (3.1). FP is fixed point, SC is synchronous chaos, CRW is chaotic rotating wave, QRW is quasiperiodic rotating wave, PRW is periodic rotating wave. Based on data from [35].

This means that all three oscillators have the same fixed point. There also exists a region of synchronous chaos (SC), where the Lyapunov spectrum contains one positive and one null exponents.

3.2. Bifurcation analysis

For higher R , the synchronized state becomes unstable through a soft blowout nonhysteretic bifurcation. This means that more and more unstable periodic orbits embedded into the synchronous attractor become transversely unstable through Andronov–Hopf bifurcations, in such a way that above a particular value of R depending on the synchronized state becomes unstable on average blowout bifurcation. This bifurcation is preceded by the phenomenon of attractor bubbling, that occurs when the system starts visiting transversely unstable periodic orbits which makes the attractor size increase. This oscillatory instability gives rise to chaotic rotating wave (CRW) born in another Hopf bifurcation. Thus, close to the onset of the bifurcation (region I in Fig. 6), a CRW is the combined dynamics stemming from chaotic

dynamics in the synchronization manifold with the oscillation introduced by the Hopf bifurcation.

For this system, the CRW is characterized by a fast oscillation compared to the time scale of the chaotic oscillation, introduced by the Hopf bifurcation. The CRW is associated with a phase difference of $2\pi N$ between neighboring oscillators where N is the number of units in the ring, superimposed to the chaotic motion. Three regions with this state depending on the Lyapunov exponents can be distinguished in Fig. 6. In regions I and III, there exists one positive and two vanishing Lyapunov exponents the degeneracy of this exponent is not theoretically proved, so it is plausible that one exponent has very small magnitude although it is indistinguishable from zero in practice. In region II, instead, there are two clearly positive and one vanishing LEs.

At larger R , there is a small region that exhibits two-frequency quasiperiodic rotating wave (QRW). The Lyapunov spectrum does not contain any positive exponent, hence chaos has disappeared, instead there are two null Lyapunov exponents which correspond to the two incommensurate frequencies of the quasiperiodic regime. Finally, for large R there exists periodic rotating wave (PRW) and, accordingly, only one Lyapunov exponent is zero, whereas the rest are negative.

3.3. Electronic circuit experiments

The experimental time series with analog electronic circuits [35] depicted in Fig. 7 showcase periodic, two-frequency quasiperiodic, three-frequency quasiperiodic, and chaotic rotating waves observed. One can see in Fig. 7(a) that the PRW at low R is characterized by the existence of a $2\pi/3$ phase shift between adjacent oscillators. This behavior can be attributed to the dominance of the complex mode with $k = 1$, while the synchronous mode with $k = 0$ remains approximately stationary.

The emergence of the second frequency in a

FIG. 7. Experimental time series representing (a) periodic rotating wave (PRW), (b) two-frequency quasiperiodic rotating wave (QRW), and (c) three-frequency quasiperiodic wave (QPW), and (d) chaotic rotation wave (CRW) in the ring of three Lorenz oscillators given by Eqs. (3.1). Based on data from [35].

supercritical Neimark–Sacker bifurcation (or 2D torus bifurcation) gives rise to the two-frequency QRW, as depicted in Fig. 7(b). As the value of R increases further, a third frequency appears in a secondary Neimark–Sacker bifurcation (or 3D torus bifurcation), leading to the three-frequency QPW shown in Fig. 7(c). The existence of stable three-frequency quasiperiodic motion has been confirmed by various numerical [53, 80–83] and experimental works [84–87].

Finally, at high values of R , the CRW is observed, as illustrated in Fig. 7(d). Despite its chaotic nature, this wave exhibits a seemingly simple behavior. The trajectory of the average of the three oscillators with mode $k = 0$ closely resembles that of an isolated Lorenz oscillator. Superimposed on this chaotic motion, each node displays an oscillating component with a phase difference of $2\pi/3$ between consecutive oscillators.

4. Ring of Rössler oscillators

In the cases mentioned earlier, the uncoupled oscillators are in a state of stable equilibrium. However, when the strength of coupling exceeds a certain threshold, the oscillators start to exhibit oscillations, giving rise to a rotating wave. This scenario is quite common, but there is another interesting phenomenon to consider. Zhang and colleagues [26] discovered that even chaotic oscillators, which are uncoupled, can generate a periodic rotating wave when they are coupled, owing to their phase synchronization [1]. Let us delve into this intriguing phenomenon in more detail.

FIG. 8. Rotating waves in the ring of (a) $N = 6$ and (b) $N = 14$ coupled Rössler oscillators given by Eqs. (4.1) for $\sigma = 0.08$ and $\sigma = 0.34$, respectively. The numbers indicate the positions of the i -th oscillator at an arbitrary instant. Based on data from [26].

4.1. Model of coupled Rössler oscillators

Consider the ring of bidirectionally coupled Rössler oscillators with diffusive coupling [26]:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{x}_1 &= -y_1 - z_1 + \sigma(x_{i+1} + x_{i-1} - 2x_i), \\ \dot{y}_1 &= x_1 + ay_1 + \sigma(y_{i+1} + y_{i-1} - 2y_i), \\ \dot{z}_1 &= b + (x_1 - c)z_1 + \sigma(z_{i+1} + z_{i-1} - 2z_i), \\ x_{i+N} &= x_i, \quad y_{i+N} = y_i, \quad z_{i+N} = z_i, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, N. \end{aligned} \tag{4.1}$$

The uncoupled oscillators, with parameters $a = 0.45$, $b = 2$, and $c = 4$, exhibit chaotic behavior. However, for certain coupling strength, the oscillators exhibit identical periodic orbits, but with distinct phases.

4.2. Periodic rotating waves

Figure 8 displays periodic rotating waves with the (x_i, y_i) projection of the phase space. In this state, each pair of nearest-neighbor oscillators exhibits an equal phase shift of T/N , where T represents the oscillation period.

The long-time average phase shift can be found as

$$\langle \Delta_{i+1,j} \rangle = \lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T [\phi_{i+1}(t) - \phi_i(t)] dt = 2\pi/N, \tag{4.2}$$

where ϕ_i is the angle of the i -th oscillator, and

$$\tan \phi_i(t) = y_i(t)/x_i(t).$$

The fundamental concept here is that the aforementioned observations can be intuitively comprehended by considering the interplay between chaos and connection. When coupling is minimal, chaos dominates and leads to a disorganized spatial distribution. Conversely, mutual coupling fosters the emergence of specific spatial orders among the oscillators, which can be characterized by the presence of coupling potential minima.

By emphasizing the chaotic motion and disregarding the amplitude fluctuations of the oscillators, specifically by assuming the oscillator motion as $x_i(t) = r \cos \phi(t)$ and $y_i(t) = r \sin \phi(t)$, we can represent the couplings described in Eqs. (4.1) in the (x, y) plane as a gradient force originating from a potential

$$\begin{aligned} H(\vec{\phi}) &= \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{1}{2} r^2 \left\{ \left[\sin(\phi_{i+1} - \sin(\phi_i)) \right]^2 \right\} \\ &+ \left[\cos(\phi_{i+1} - \cos(\phi_i)) \right]^2 \\ &= r^2 \left[N - \sum_{i=1}^N \cos(\Delta_{i+1,i}) \right], \end{aligned}$$

where $\vec{\phi} = (\phi_1, \phi_2, \dots, \phi_N)$.

The objective of this coupling is to align the phase distribution towards the potential's minima. It can be readily demonstrated that for equal phase differences

$$\Delta_{2,1} = \Delta_{3,2} = \dots = \Delta_{1,N} = \Delta = 2k\pi/N, \tag{4.3}$$

where $k = 1, 2, \dots \leq N/2$, the potential exhibits extrema values characterized by $\partial H(\vec{\phi})/\partial \phi_i = 0$. The condition that is both necessary and sufficient for any of these extrema to be minima is $\cos \Delta > 0$, which can be equivalently expressed as $|\Delta| < \pi/4$.

Now we can comprehend the key findings concerning the chaos-coupling competition. For $N < 4$, neither chaos nor coupling promotes

the existence of an ordered antiphase state. As a result, we cannot observe any periodic rotating wave. In the case of $N \geq 4$, although coupling can facilitate certain ordered configurations described by Eq. (4.3) with minimal potential, chaos still strives to disrupt any form of order. The competition between chaos and coupling produces varying outcomes depending on the intensity of coupling.

5. Ring of lasers

Next, consider the main results of the study of rotating wave in laser systems.

Despite extensive research on the dynamics of solitary lasers [88–93], there remains a notable gap in the comprehensive investigation of coupled lasers in various coupling configurations. When examining the dynamics in ring-coupled lasers, it is crucial to acknowledge prior investigations conducted on semiconductor lasers [53, 94, 95], which predominantly focused on synchronization phenomena [1].

When reviewing the dynamics in ring-coupled lasers, it is important to acknowledge previous investigations on semiconductor lasers [53, 94, 95] which were mainly focused on their synchronization. In these studies, the main identified route to chaos in such ring configurations was as follows. Initially, the individual lasers operate in a continuous-wave regime, but as the coupling strength is increased, they transition into a periodic regime. With further increases in coupling, a series of Hopf bifurcations occur, giving rise to quasiperiodic and chaotic oscillations [53]. Within the chaotic range, synchronization states emerge, spanning from asynchronous behavior to phase and almost synchronization. Although previous studies did not specifically investigate rotating waves, their occurrence in the laser ring is highly likely. Thus, it is crucial to pay careful attention to this aspect in future research.

Over the past few decades, there has been an extraordinary surge in research and the

commercialization of fiber lasers, resulting in significant advancements. These lasers have undergone a revolutionary transformation, primarily fueled by their widespread utilization in various fields, such as optical communications, optical sensing, laser surgery, nonlinear optics, and optical materials [96]. Additionally, fiber amplifier technology has emerged as an exceptionally practical platform for industrial applications. Its compactness, robustness, reliability, and high efficiency make it particularly well-suited for such purposes. Moreover, the alignment-free structure and spatial beam profile further enhance its appeal in industrial settings.

5.1. Model of coupled Er-doped fiber lasers

Erbium-doped fiber lasers (EDFLs) offer a multitude of advantages that make them highly suitable for various applications [96]. Firstly, their compact size allows for seamless integration into optical communication networks, simplifying their incorporation into existing infrastructure. Secondly, the utilization of a laser wavelength, particularly around 1550 nm, is widely adopted in optical communication systems due to its low losses in optical fibers. This wavelength facilitates efficient transmission over long distances, ensuring minimal signal degradation.

Moreover, EDFLs showcase a wide array of dynamic behaviors, encompassing period doubling, chaos, and multistability [88, 90]. These dynamical characteristics can be effectively controlled and harnessed, not only for chaotic communication [97], but also for a plethora of other applications. For example, EDFLs find utility in various domains such as spectral interferometry [98], optical coherence tomography [99], optical sensing [100], optical metrology [101], industrial micromachining [102], LIDAR systems [103], and medicine [104]. The versatility of EDFLs expands their potential beyond communication, enabling their deployment in

diverse fields that can leverage their unique dynamical properties.

The dynamics of the ring of three unidirectionally coupled EDFLs can be mathematically described using two differential equations that represent the laser intensity x_j ($j = 1, 2, 3$) and the population inversion y_j . These equations are given as follows [54]:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dx_j}{d\theta} &= ax_jy_j - bx_j + c(y_j + 0.3075), \\ \frac{dy_j}{d\theta} &= dx_jy_j - (y_j + 0.3075) + P_{pmod_j} \left\{ 1 - \exp \left[-18 \left(1 - \frac{1 - (y_j + 0.3075)}{0.6150} \right) \right] \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (5.1)$$

with pumping

$$P_{pmod_j} = 506[1 + k(x_{j-1} - x_j)], \quad (5.2)$$

where k is the coupling coefficient, x_j and y_j are the laser intensity and population inversion with the following parameters: $a = 6.62 \times 10^7$, $b = 7.4151 \times 10^6$, $c = 0.0163$, $d = 4.0763 \times 10^3$.

5.2. Rotating waves in the ring of EDFLs

Let us examine the phenomenon of rotating waves in a ring of unidirectionally coupled EDFLs. These rotating waves emerge from the phase disparity between adjacent lasers and propagate along the ring structure.

The rotating wave dynamics in the EDFL ring is illustrated in Fig. 9 for four distinct coupling strengths: $k = 2.58$, $k = 3.82$, $k = 5.49$, and $k = 5.84$. In these plots, the oscillators only differ in their initial phases, resulting in phase shifts at each successive node. Consequently, rotating waves are formed within the cyclic ring. The left column of the figure illustrates the two-dimensional time series patterns of the three lasers, clearly displaying oblique stripes that signify the presence of rotating waves. The inclination of these stripes indicates the wave propagation speed. The right column presents the

FIG. 9. (Left) Rotating wave and (right) phase portraits for a) $k = 2.58$ (periodic wave), b) $k = 3.82$ (quasiperiodic wave) (2D torus), c) $k = 5.49$ (quasiperiodic wave) (3D torus), and d) $k = 5.84$ (chaotic wave). The color in the left column indicates the laser intensity. (Color online)

phase portraits of the corresponding attractors, which remain identical for all oscillators due to the system’s symmetry. Notably, as the coupling strength is increased, the size of the attractor expands.

Figure 9 displays various types of rotating waves: a) periodic, b) quasiperiodic with two frequencies in the 2D torus region, c) quasiperiodic with three frequencies in the 3D

FIG. 10. (a,c) Phase portraits and (b,d) power spectra of coexisting (a,b) periodic and (c,d) chaotic rotating waves at $k = 14.08$. f_w is the wave frequency.

torus region, and d) chaotic. By examining the slope of the strips in the figure, it becomes evident that an increase in the coupling strength k leads to decreasing speed of the rotating wave. Moreover, when the wave becomes chaotic, it ceases to propagate and transforms into a standing wave (vertical strips in Fig. 9(d)).

5.3. Coexistence of rotating waves

Furthermore, it has been discovered that within a specific range of the coupling strength ($13 < k_6 < 14.81$), periodic and chaotic waves coexist. This finding aligns with observations made in the context of a ring of coupled Duffing oscillators (refer to Section II).

Figure 10 exhibits the phase portraits and their respective power spectra of coexisting periodic and chaotic waves. In the power spectrum of the periodic orbit (Fig. 10(b)), the wave frequency f_w and its harmonics can be discerned. Conversely, the power spectrum of the chaotic wave (Fig. 10(d)) is broad and lacks a dominant frequency.

Finally, it is essential to acknowledge the limitations of this study. The investigation primarily focused on the simplest configuration of a three-laser ring, and therefore, the conclusions drawn may not directly extrapolate to larger laser networks. Nevertheless, certain dynamical characteristics exhibited by this system can potentially be extended to larger laser networks, thus warranting further investigation in future research endeavors.

6. Ring of neural oscillators

Finally, we review the main contribution in the study of rotating waves in neuronal models.

Neural networks featuring unidirectional ring topologies play a crucial role in modeling neuronal dynamics and studying information processing in the fields of neuroscience and medicine. Ring neural motifs are particularly significant in the generation of stable periodic motor commands by the central pattern generator, a component of the nervous system responsible for controlling rhythmic locomotion in animals [105]. Furthermore, a ring-type topology can be observed in the sequential feed-forward neuronal projections of the cortico-striatal-basal ganglia-thalamo-cortical motor loop, which is relevant to the understanding of Parkinson's disease and its pathogenesis [106]. Therefore, the study of rotating waves in neuronal models is of high importance.

The study of rotating waves in unidirectional rings of coupled neurons has been conducted by Horikawa and Kitajima[55] as well as by Perlikowski et al. [47]. Horikawa and Kitajima employed a simple sigmoidal function to model the neuron, whereas Perlikowski et al. utilized the more sophisticated FitzHugh–Nagumo (FHN) model. However, both studies successfully demonstrated the presence of rotating waves. Given that the FHN model yields more accurate results, we will focus our review on the findings derived from this model.

FIG. 11. Ring of unidirectionally coupled neural oscillators. τ_j are coupling delays.

6.1. Model of FitzHugh–Nagumo neurons

The interesting research was conducted by Perlikowski et al. [47], who discovered rotating waves in the unidirectional ring composed of FHN delay-coupled spiking neurons. The ring configuration is shown in Fig. 11.

These neurons interact through excitatory chemical synapses. The emergence of rotating waves is facilitated by Hopf bifurcations of the symmetric equilibrium. Notably, they found that the introduction of delays in the coupling creates multiple rotating waves.

The dynamics of the ring of FHN neurons unidirectionally coupled by chemical synapses is modelled by the following equations:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{v}_j &= v_j - v_j^3/3 - w_j + I_j + C(V - v_j)s_{j+1}(t - \tau), \\ \dot{w}_j &= 0.08(v_j + 0.7 - 0.8w_j), \\ \dot{s}_j &= 0.5 \frac{1 - s_j}{1 + \exp[-4(v_j - 1.5)]} - 0.6s_j, \end{aligned} \tag{6.1}$$

where v_j and w_j ($j = 1, 2, \dots, N$) are respectively fast and slow variables, associated with the membrane potential and sodium channel reactivation and potassium channel deactivation of a single neural cell j , s_j is a postsynaptic potential which models synaptic coupling, I_j is an external input regulating neural spiking dynamics, randomly Gaussian distributed around

the mean value $\bar{I} = 0.4$ with standard deviation $\sigma = 0.005$, C is the coupling strength, and τ is the delay time. The reversal potential $V = 2$ models excitatory coupling. The unidirectional ring configuration is modelled by $s_{N+1} = s_1$.

Due to the spatiotemporal symmetries, the system of Eqs. (6.1) has periodic solutions in the form of rotating waves:

$$z_j(t) = a \exp(i\varphi_l j + i\omega t), \tag{6.2}$$

where $\varphi_l = 2\pi l/N$ ($1 \leq l \leq N$), a and ω are unknown amplitude and frequency of the periodic solutions, respectively.

6.2. Multiple rotating waves

Figure 12 illustrates spatial dynamics of a ring consisting of 200 spiking neurons in the absent of the delay in coupling (Fig. 12(a)) and with delay $\tau = 0.03$ (Fig. 12(b)). The synchronous states forming rotating waves propagating with different speeds and frequencies depend on the initial conditions.

Consider, first, the patterns in the ring without delay ($\tau = 0$) illustrated in Fig. 12(a). The uncoupled neurons ($C = 0$) fire asynchronously resulting in randomly distributed black circles, i.e., no wave patterns are observed. However, as the coupling strength is increased, multiple rotating waves arise. It is worth noting that depending on the initial conditions, the frequency of the synchronized states can take on different values, indicating the existence of multistability in the synchronized regimes.

For instance, with coupling strength $C = 5$ and narrowly distributed initial conditions, the neurons synchronize at frequency $f_j = 18.2$, leading to the emergence of a standing wave pattern (indicated by vertical red circles). However, for broadly distributed initial conditions, the neurons synchronize at either $f_j = 18.8$ or $f_j = 17.7$, resulting in the formation of firing fronts depicted by green and blue circles, respectively. In these synchronized states, two firing fronts propagate along the ring,

FIG. 12. Synchronized spatial patterns in the ring of $N = 200$ unidirectionally synaptically coupled spiking neurons modelled by Eqs. (6.1). (a) Rotating waves in the ring of coupled neurons without delay. Non uniformly distributed black circles – asynchronous firing at $C = 0$, vertically arranged red circles – in-phase synchronization at $C = 5$ and $m = 0$, green circles arranged along lines with negative slope – two rotating waves propagating in the direction of the coupling at $C = 5$ and $m = 2$, blue circles arranged along lines with positive slope – two rotating waves propagating in opposite direction of the coupling at $C = 5$ and $m = -2$. (b) Two coexisting rotating waves of the neuronal firing with delay $\tau = 0.03$ and $C = 5$. The black and grey lines indicate the onsets of spikes for different initial conditions. Based on data from [47]. (Color online)

with each neuron firing only after its neighboring neuron generates a spike. Remarkably, these firing fronts can travel either in the direction of the synaptic coupling or in the opposite direction. As described in Section II, the direction of wave propagation can be determined by analyzing the slope of the lines displayed in Fig. 12. If the lines exhibit a slant towards the right, it indicates that the wave is propagating in the opposite direction of the coupling. Conversely, a leftward tilt indicates propagation in the direction of the coupling.

To explore the coexistence of different rotating waves, the initial conditions are considered to be distributed on a limit cycle $[v(t), w(t), s(t)] = \gamma(t)$, where $t \in [0, T]$, of

a single neural oscillator, and T represents a period of oscillations. Utilizing Eq. (6.2), for a fixed integer l , the initial conditions are taken as $[v_j(0), w_j(0), s_j(0)] = \gamma(t_j)$, where $t_j = jT/N \bmod T$. Employing this approach, the above-mentioned synchronized states are obtained with different synchronized frequencies for $l = 0, 2$, and -2 .

In addition to different frequencies, synchronized neurons display distinct spatial organizations of spiking dynamics. For narrowly distributed initial conditions, such as for $l = 0$, the oscillators are in-phase synchronized, and all neurons fire simultaneously (Fig. 12(a), red circles). Conversely, for broadly distributed initial conditions, the neuronal activity can be organized in a rotating-wave regime where one or several firing fronts travel along the ring. In this regime, each neuron fires after its neighboring neuron generates a spike. Interestingly, the firing fronts can move along the ring either in the direction of the synaptic coupling or in the opposite direction. For instance, for $l = 2$, there exist two rotating waves propagating along the ring in the direction of the coupling (counterclockwise), represented by green circles. Conversely, when $l = -2$, the two rotating waves propagate along the ring in the opposite direction of the coupling (in the clockwise direction), illustrated by blue circles. It is essential to emphasize that uncoupled and desynchronized neurons do not exhibit any distinguishable spatial structure, as depicted by black circles in the figures.

6.3. Delay-induced multistability

The number of coexisting rotating waves with different speeds and frequencies increases with delay time τ .

Figure 12(b) illustrates the presence of two coexisting rotating waves for delay $\tau = 0.03$. The spatial patterns in the figure show two sets of lines, one black and one grey, slanted towards the left. This indicates that the two rotating waves propagate in the direction of the coupling, each

with its own distinct velocity.

Notably, the spatial velocity of wave propagation along the ring significantly decreases as the number of coexisting waves increases. Additionally, it was observed that stronger coupling without any delay tends to destabilize the rotating waves. However, this situation changes when there is a delay in the coupling between the neurons. Interestingly, stronger coupling in the presence of a delay appears to enhance the stability of the rotating waves.

Thus, the investigation of rotating waves in the ring of coupled FHN neurons has yielded intriguing and unexpected findings. Despite the presence of purely unidirectional coupling in the model, it has been observed that waves can propagate in the opposite direction of the coupling. Furthermore, the firing patterns of neurons within the ring can exhibit coincidental firing, sequential firing corresponding to the directionality of coupling, or even firing in reverse order, with a timing sequence completely opposite to the direction of coupling. These findings challenge the conventional approach used by neuroscientists to associate timing sequences with coupling patterns and highlight the potential for significant misinterpretations. It underscores the need for a careful reconsideration of the relationship between firing patterns and coupling dynamics in neural systems.

7. Conclusions and insights into working memory models

In conclusion, this review paper has presented a comprehensive survey of the research conducted on rotating waves observed in rings of coupled identical oscillators. The emergence of these stable periodic orbits due to phase differences between neighboring oscillators has been observed in various nonlinear systems, spanning electrical circuits, neural models, Lorenz and Duffing oscillators, and more. We demonstrated the influence of coupling strength and the number of oscillators on the behavior of

rotating waves, including their shape, speed, and frequency.

To comprehend the intricate dynamics of rotating waves, a range of techniques has been employed, encompassing time series analysis, phase-space analysis, bifurcation diagrams, and basins of attraction. These methodologies have successfully unraveled the complex routes from coexisting stable equilibria to hyperchaos, elucidating a sequence of bifurcations such as Hopf, torus, and crisis bifurcations. Additionally, the study has revealed the coexistence of multiple rotating waves under the same system parameters.

The insights garnered from this extensive body of research on rotating waves have far-reaching implications and can act as a catalyst for further exploration and application across numerous scientific disciplines. They provide valuable understanding of the underlying mechanisms governing rotating waves in real-world systems, including lasers, cardiorespiratory systems, neural networks, and beyond. By expanding our knowledge in this field, we are better equipped to harness the potential of rotating waves for technological advancements, as well as gain deeper insights into the fundamental principles that govern complex dynamical systems.

Despite extensive research on rotating waves in various dynamical systems, many unanswered questions persist in this field. Of particular challenge is the investigation of rotating waves within neural networks of the brain, as it holds the potential to unravel the underlying mechanisms of working memory. Notably, several scientists have posited that the neural network structure in the brain is closely linked to short-time (or working) memory [107–111]. Working memory is defined as a limited capacity system for the temporary storage and manipulation of information for cognitive tasks [112, 113]. It entails a transient amplification of neuronal activity, lasting from milliseconds to seconds [114].

The phenomenon of sustained activity in local brain circuits, even in the absence of

external stimulation, has been observed in diverse brain regions, including the prefrontal cortex and thalamus [115–117]. To explore specific phenomena observed in vivo, such as persistent activity [118] and information transmission [119], researchers have utilized the network geometry method in vitro. This approach enables the examination of these phenomena within a controlled experimental setting, providing valuable insights into the network structure of working memory and the corresponding neural dynamics.

Given that the connections between brain neurons primarily occur through chemical synapses, the neural rings formed are typically unidirectional. In this regard, a crucial question arises: How do the speeds of wave propagation in neural rings depend on the number of neurons within the ring?

Furthermore, it is important to note that a single neuron can participate in multiple memory loops. To illustrate, consider the process of memorizing a friend's phone number. This information forms a memory loop dedicated to storing the phone number itself. Simultaneously, this loop is connected to other loops that hold memories associated with your friend's characteristics, such as his/her personality traits or physical appearance. In this way, the neural network enables the integration of various memory loops, facilitating the retrieval and association of related information. Hence, memory loops exhibit intricate neural interconnections to form complex intertwined high-order networks.

Each neuron in such a network can participate in distinct elementary memory loops, contributing to its functional versatility. A similar phenomenon can be observed in social networks, where an individual may be part of various social groups, each involving different roles and interactions. For instance, a person can simultaneously be a member of a family, a colleague in an office, and a player in a sports team, among others. This multifaceted involvement exemplifies the complexity and

FIG. 13. Coupled rings of oscillators with two rotating waves.

adaptability present in both neural and social systems.

Figure 13 illustrates an instance of two interconnected rings, providing a visual representation of this concept. Within this network, the nodes in both the larger and smaller rings generate rotating waves characterized by distinct frequencies. Due to the relationship between wave speed and the number of nodes, it is anticipated that these two waves will circulate along their respective rings at different velocities. An intriguing question arises: what will transpire when one wave overtakes the other? To gain insights into wave dynamics and their interactions in such scenarios, further investigation is warranted. Advancing our understanding in this area will contribute to unraveling the complexities underlying memory processes within neural networks.

The initial exploration in this domain was undertaken by Nagao et al. [48], who examined the dynamics of a ring of delay-coupled electrochemical reactions. In their investigation, each oscillator was not only coupled with its immediate neighbor but also with the preceding neighbor. They demonstrate that the interaction of various rotating waves creates complex patterns of multiple waves and even oscillation death. While this system is unrelated to neurons,

the methodology employed by the researchers can be adapted for the study of neuronal networks.

The analysis and characterization of rotating waves have far-reaching implications, particularly in the fields of neuroscience and medicine. These phenomena provide valuable insights into

cardiorespiratory interactions, traveling electrical waves in the cortex, and similar phenomena. Understanding the dynamics of rotating waves offers potential applications in the diagnosis and treatment of neurological disorders and cardiac arrhythmias [120].

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